

On manipulating the thermoelectric potential of *p*-type ZnO by nano-structuring

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Abstract

Throughout this work, ZnO nanoparticles were produced by a simple co-precipitation method, in which the volume of the basic solution (NaOH, 5–30 ml) was varied to understand its effect on the properties of the nanoparticles. A structural and morphological effect was observed, namely a change in reflections between $2\theta = 31.75^\circ$ (100) and $2\theta = 34.4^\circ$ (002) peaks. At the same time, The nanoparticles change from a hexagonal prism shape to a *desert-rose stones* structure for high base concentrations. The transport measurements were performed from room temperature up to 340 K. At room temperature, a correlation between the Seebeck coefficient and the electrical conductivity was achieved, whereas the thermal conductivity behaves distinctly. A thermal conductivity value of $0.5 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ was observed, which is two orders of magnitude lower than the bulk counterpart. The behaviours of the *PF* and *ZT* also reveal the different influences of the electrons and the phonons for the different nanostructures, since the electronic phenomena predominate in the hexagonal prism structures, the phonon phenomena predominate in the *desert-rose stones*, due to the reduced dimension of these structures. For higher temperatures, a thermal activation model was used to determine the Activation Energy (E_a), leading to values in the hundredths of meV range, with higher values for the volumes of NaOH where a mixture of the two types of structures is observed, where the presence of different interfaces created a barrier for the carriers to pass from grain to grain.

Keywords: thermoelectric, ZnO, nanostructures, co-precipitation, Thermal Activation Theory

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1. Introduction

With the continuous development of hi-tech devices and sensors in today's society, there is an emerging demand for new energy resources, that should be cleaner and environmentally friendly[1]. Energy harvesting appears as an alternative to overcome this demand, namely by triboelectricity[2, 3], piezoelectricity[4] or even thermoelectricity[5]. The last one is promising since it consists of the direct conversion of heat into electricity, or vice-versa. The phenomena occur when a temperature gradient (ΔT) is applied in a thermoelectric (TE) material, a potential gradient (ΔV) is formed in the conduction band, *i.e.*, the mobile charges from the hot side (higher energy) tend to diffuse to the cold side (lower energy). This effect is called the Seebeck Effect (S)[6]. The efficiency of a TE material is parameterized by its Figure of Merit (ZT) that is defined as $ZT = S^2\sigma T/\kappa$, where σ is the electrical conductivity, and κ is the thermal conductivity. The κ is constituted by two components, the lattice (κ_l) and the electronic contributions (κ_e) - $\kappa = \kappa_l + \kappa_e$ [7]. Since the transport properties are interrelated, one of the strategies to enhance the ZT value of a material is to manipulate the lattice component of κ , since its electronic component is related to the σ [8, 9]. This manipulation can be achieved by reducing the phonon mean free path due to interface scattering, creating a barrier for heat diffusion[10]. Considering that these effects occur at the nanoscale, nanostructuring bulk materials confers significant advantages[11–13].

Due to the temperature dependence of the TE properties, there are different operation temperatures, *i.e.*, the range of temperatures for which the TE efficiency of a material is maximum. As a result, three ranges for the operation of TE materials, low-, mid- and high-temperatures were established, where they reveal higher efficiencies[14]. For instance, in the low-temperature range, *i.e.* near room-temperature (300 K-400 K), the most predominant materials are the semiconductors, such as Bi-Te alloys, namely BiSbTe as p-type ($ZT = 1.3 @ 350 \text{ K}$) [15] and $\text{Bi}_{1.8}\text{Sb}_{0.2}\text{Te}_{2.7}\text{Se}_{0.3} + 15 \text{ wt\% Te}$ as n-type ($ZT = 1.4 @ \sim 400 \text{ K}$)[16]. Concerning the mid-temperature applications (400 K – 900 K), these temperatures are not sufficiently higher to compromise the stability of the TE material and correspond to the larger fraction of potentially available wasted heat[17]. CoSb₃-based skutterudites are a good example for this temperature range due to their high-performance, low-toxic, high-stability, and mechanical robust features, reaching a $ZT \sim 0.65 @ 623 \text{ K}$ [18]. One remarkable example is the work

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reported by Hinterleitner *et al.*[19] showing the achievement of ZT values close to 6 at approximately 400 K, using thin-film Heusler alloys based on $\text{Fe}_2\text{V}_{0.8}\text{W}_{0.2}\text{Al}$ prepared by magnetron sputtering, deposited on a Si substrate, being a significant breakthrough in the area. Despite their great performance, the most common alloys tend to be toxic, not environmentally friendly, and scarce as natural resources, besides being materials with low thermal or chemical stabilities, reducing their usage to oxygen-free environments[20]. On the other hand, oxide semiconductors present high stability at high temperatures in air, non-toxicity, reduced costs and meagre environmental impact, becoming a reliable solution for the recovery of decentralized waste heat energy for higher energy efficiency[21]. Additionally, since the TE efficiency depends directly on the Carnot efficiency cycle, materials with higher operating temperatures can present higher efficiencies. Since oxides have great thermal stability, they can be considered strong candidates for high-temperature systems (> 900 K), when compared with conventional alloy-based modules[22].

Although several families of oxides reveal capacities for TE applications, there are two main groups that gained interest over the years due to their superior performance[23], namely, the Na_xCoO_2 [24] and related layered compounds (*p*-type)[25], and some of the degenerate semiconductors (*n*-type), such as doped SrTiO_3 [26] or CaMnO_3 perovskites[27], doped ZnO [28], or doped In_2O_3 bixbyite[29]. For instance, Fujita *et al.*[30] performed one of the most notable results in this field by producing $\text{Na}_x\text{CoO}_{2-\delta}$ single crystals being able to reach a $ZT = 1.2$ for high temperatures (800 K) and despite its efficiency at room temperature remains low, playing with oxygen vacancies led to a huge impact in the ZT value. In 2012, in a different family of materials, Li *et al.*[31] reported a high ZT value of 1.1 at 923 K in the BiCuSeO , synthesized by a two-step solid-state reaction route, by doping it with Ba and tuning the grain sizes. These two methods allowed a decrease in κ by point defect scattering through Ba doping, and confinement and scattering of phonons in layer interfaces.

Between these tendencies, ZnO emerged as potential TE material due to their established versatility on band structures tailoring since it is a wide bandgap semiconductor (3.37eV)[32]. As a TE material, it presents a high S , but its κ remains relatively high and the σ is very low, thus the improvement of its efficiency continues to be a challenge[33]. The simplest way to tune the ZT in these materials is through the doping process. Several elements have been

used to improve the ZT , such as Al, Ga and Ni[34, 35]. For instance, Jantrasee *et al.*[36] reported an increase of the ZT value (0.28 at 700 K) by two orders of magnitude higher than pure ZnO using just 3% Al-doped ZnO. Ohtaki *et al.* [37] reinforced the necessity of doping ZnO and by dual doping with Al and Ga ($Zn_{0.96}Al_{0.02}Ga_{0.02}O$), and ZT values of 0.47 at 1000 K and 0.65 at 1247 K were achieved. The nature of these improvements relates to the use of dopants with heavier atomic mass than the Zn atom, contributing to the decrease of the κ_l by mass fluctuations[38]. Another approach to tune the ZT is related to microstructuring the ZnO. For instance, Zhao *et al.*[39] achieved a 52% decrease of the thermal conductivity, compared with the bulk ZnO, by using a self-assembled layered and correlated grain structure. Although the results from doping ZnO can be very promising, nano-structuration can bring other benefits due to the introduction of quantum confinement effects to increase power factors and also of many internal interfaces to scatter phonons, as previously suggested[40]. This had been proved by the recent work reported by Kim *et al.*[41], whose work focuses on the use of ZnO ultrathin nanoshell structures. Due to the reduction of κ by ~ 38 times compared with a 3.2 μm ZnO film, a ZT of ~ 0.017 at 333 K was obtained. With this TE material, a prototype was fabricated, being able to generate ~ 60 mV at a temperature difference of 40 K. Thus topology and nanostructuration unveil to play an important role in the TE efficiency of ZnO.

In the literature, it is possible to find a large variety of ZnO nanostructures[42]. At 1D, ZnO nanostructures have the most diverse shapes, such as rods [43], tubes [44], wires [45], rings [46], helixes and springs [47], ribbons [48], and combs [49]. In terms of 2D structures, they can exist as nanosheets [50] or nanopellets [51]. Lastly, the ZnO 3D structures include flower [52], dandelion [53], snowflakes [54], coniferous urchin-like [55], among others. Although ZnO nanostructures present a clear role on the TE, as well as diversified structures at different dimensions, their potential in the TE field is far from being fully exploited.

The present work will tackle the viability of ZnO nanoparticles as a TE material the influence of structure and morphology and their impact in the transport properties. These different morphologic structures were tailored by changing synthesis conditions, namely, by changing the volume base solvent NaOH ranging from 5 up to 30 ml.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials Preparation

In the present work, Zinc Oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were produced by the coprecipitation method, based on the one presented by Osman and Mustafa[56]. This procedure consists of the addition of a basic solution to provide the oxide ions to an acid solution that contains the Zn ions. For that, it was used Zinc Acetate 2-Hydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Reag. Ph. Eur.) from *Panreac* and Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) (98.6 %) in lentils purchased from *José Manuel Gomes dos Santos, Lda*. Firstly, a solution of $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved in bi-deionized water, in a concentration of 0.27 M, and, secondly, a solution of NaOH, using bi-deionized water, in a concentration of 1.2 M, were prepared. Then, the NaOH solution (pH=14) was added to the Zinc Acetate solution (pH=5), drop by drop, until the occurrence of precipitation. Herein, different volumes of NaOH were used to produce different of ZnO nanoparticles, *i.e.*, 5 ml, 10 ml, 12 ml, 15 ml, 20 ml and 30 ml, and all nanoparticles were produced maintaining the same production conditions except the volume of NaOH, to ensure reproducibility. After the formation of the precipitate, the solution was washed with deionized water 6 times to reduce the concentration of Na^+ ions. This process was performed by centrifuging the solution at 10000 rpm for 5 min. The process follows the following chemical equations [56]:

At the end of the washes, the deposited was dried in the oven for 12 hours at 80 °C. Then, the powder was pressed into a pellet with 1.3 cm of diameter using 4000 psi during 40 s with the aim to further measure the transport properties.

2.2. Characterization Techniques

The crystallography analysis was performed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) in a SmartLab Rigaku® diffractometer at room temperature (RT) over a range of $2\theta = 10 - 90^\circ$ in a Bragg-

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Brentano $\theta/2\theta$ configuration using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.540593 \text{ \AA}$, with a current of 200 mA and a voltage of 45 kV. The morphological examination of the samples was evaluated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) using a *Phillips-FEI/Quanta 400 FEG*, from Materials Center of the University of Porto (CEMUP), with a coupled *SEM/EDAX Genesis X4M*.

The crystallite size of the samples was calculated using the Williamson - Hall method [57] which is expressed by:

$$\beta \cos \theta = K\lambda/D + 4\epsilon \sin \theta \quad (5)$$

where D is the crystalline size and ϵ is the lattice strain. Plotting $\beta \cos \theta$ against $4 \sin \theta$, and doing a simple linear fit, ϵ , the intercept, $K\lambda/D$, and the value of D can be extracted. These quantities were estimated using PDXL software.

Considering the transport properties, the Seebeck Coefficient (S), Electrical Conductivity (σ) and Thermal Conductivity (κ) measurements were performed for all samples produced in the present work. Due to the difficulty in measuring S in resistive samples, a proper method to measure S at RT was developed. Electrical measurements on a solid sample require forming at least two electrical contacts to the sample. The departure of these contacts from ohmicity can cause substantial errors. In the TE measurements on oxide semiconductors, these errors are particularly detrimental as the Seebeck voltage generated along the sample can be of the same order of magnitude or smaller than the metal-metal oxide contact potential[58]. Zinc Oxide is known for being a high resistive material at RT, with a resistance in the range of 1 G Ω , making it difficult to measure the S using the conventional setups. In this way, a new set-up based on the "zero-current" technique was developed, as referred by Hossein-Babaei *et al.* [58], to determine S and estimate the resistance value for each sample. Regarding the measurements for high temperatures, it was also used this method, heating of the samples up to 380 K, and the measurement temperature estimated by the average of the temperature of the hot and cold sides. Regarding the σ determination, the sample's geometry must be taken into consideration, using a correction factor. Due to the cylindrical nature of the samples, the correction factor depends on the ratio of the probe to cylinder diameter and on the ratio of sample thickness to probe separation. Thus, σ is given by

$$\sigma = \ln(\sinh(t/s)/\sinh(t/2s))/(R\pi t) \quad (6)$$

where R is the resistance of the sample, estimated using the "zero-current" method, s is the distance between the probes and, t is the thickness of the sample. The thermal conductivity of the samples was measured using a set-up based on a steady-state method, as reported by Pires *et al.*[59]. The system is composed of a hot part heated by an internal resistance connected to a current supply, and the cold part established by a flow of cooled water. Two thermocouples are used to ensure the temperature difference between the two faces of the material. The thermal conductivity is obtained through the Fourier's law of heat conduction, given by

$$\kappa = Qt/(A\Delta T) \quad (7)$$

where $Q = VI = P$, t is the thickness, and A is the area of the sample.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1.a displays the X-ray diffractograms of the different ZnO nanoparticles, synthesized with different volumes of NaOH, *i.e.*, 5 ml, 10 ml, 12 ml, 15 ml, 20 ml and 30 ml, respectively, over a range of $2\theta = 10 - 90^\circ$.

Figure 1: (a) XRD diffractogram of the different samples of ZnO nanoparticles according to the volume of NaOH added during the co-precipitation process. The highlighted reflections (*) correspond to the additional reflections caused by the presence of Na^+ in the samples. The inset shows the change of intensity of the peaks the reflections $2\theta = 31.75^\circ$ (100) and $2\theta = 34.4^\circ$ (002). (b) Schematic representation of the hexagonal lattice unit, illustrating the a_1 , a_2 , a_3 and c axes and the basal, prism and pyramidal planes.

The main reflections presented in the diffractograms were identified and indexed to the respective Miller index, namely $2\theta = 31.75^\circ$ (100) , $2\theta = 34.4^\circ$ (002) , $2\theta = 36.13^\circ$ (101) , $2\theta = 47.42^\circ$ (102) and $2\theta = 56.45^\circ$ (110), corresponding to the *Wurtzite* hexagonal structure (JCPDS no. 036-1451; $P6_3mc$ space group). It should be noticed that additional minor reflections can be observed in the XRD patterns of 5 ml and 10 ml samples (reflections highlighted in Figure 1.a). These peaks are caused by the presence of Na^+ ions, resulting from the precipitation processes, that can be removed in the future by additional thermal treatment to obtain the Wurtzite pure phase[56]. Although the positions of the reflections are unchanged, a shift in the preferential direction between the reflections $2\theta = 31.75^\circ$ (100) and $2\theta = 34.4^\circ$ (002) peaks is observed (see inset of Figure 1.a). In Figure 2.a depicts in more detail this shift by presenting the ratio between $I(002)$ and $I(100)$ as a function of the NaOH volume.

In this graph, it is possible to observe two distinct stages, *i.e.*, a linear behaviour between 5ml to 15 ml, and a saturation point for volumes higher than 15 ml. This change is an indication that there is a two regimes state, one where the particles grow along the prism plane and then changing for the basal plane (see Figure 1.b).

Additionally, the Williamson-Hall method was used to determine the crystallite size of the samples (eq. 5), that influence the broadness of the peaks[57]. The results of these calculations are plotted in Figure 2.b, for each sample. It is possible to identify that, with the exception of 5ml, a decrease of the crystallite size, going from 43 nm at $V(NaOH) = 10$ ml to 23 nm at $V(NaOH) = 30$ ml.

Figure 2: (a) Ratio between the intensities of the peaks corresponding to the direction (002) and (100), as a function of the volume of NaOH. (b) Crystallite Size and lattice strain of each sample. The presented lines are a guide to the eye.

Figure 3: SEM images of ZnO nanoparticles with a magnification of 50 000x, for different concentrations of added NaOH: (a) 5 ml; (b) 10 ml; (c) 12 ml; (d) 15 ml; (e) 20 ml; (f) 30 ml.

Figure 3 depicts the morphological characterization of the powders produced in this work. Analyzing the morphology of the particles, with 5 ml of NaOH (see Figure 3.a), they present a hexagonal prism shape resembling hexagonal nanowires, thus showing an organized compacted hexagonal crystallographic structure[60].

The nanowires have an average hexagonal lateral size of 303 ± 11 nm and a length of 588 ± 50 nm. Comparing these particle sizes with the crystallite size, it can be concluded that several thousands of crystallites constitute each nanoparticle, having a polycrystalline character. With the addition increase of NaOH volume, it is noticeable that the shape of the particles changes, being observed the growth of a sharper structure - *desert-rose stone*[61], as depicted in Figure 3.b-f. This growth of the grain is called coalescence of the grain[62], resulting in thinner 2D plates (10—30 nm thickness) (see inset of Figure 3.d). It can also be seen that for the intermediate concentrations (10 ml and 12 ml) where the change of preferential directions occurs, in the XRD (see Figure 1.a), there is a mixture of formats of the

particles meaning that the increase of the base NaOH during the co-precipitation synthesis is favouring the formation of plates instead of an organized hexagonal compact structure. After the formation of the *desert-rose stone* structures (see Figure 3.d), these start to gather to form clusters at the microscale as confirmed in Figure 3.d-f.

Figure 4: (a) Seebeck Coefficient and Electrical Conductivity as functions of the volume of the added NaOH; (b) Linear behaviour of S vs $\sigma^{-2/3}$ (fit given by the dashed line). (c) Thermal Conductivity as a function of the volume of the added NaOH, with the corresponding nanostructures and dimensions. (d) Figure of Merit and Power Factor of ZnO, as functions of the volume of the added NaOH. The thick lines are a guide to the eye.

As a potential TE material, the evaluation of its transport properties is vital. In Figure 4 it is depicted the values of transport properties (S , σ and κ) achieved for the different produced powders. Concerning the S results, positive values were obtained, meaning that the produced ZnO is a p-type material, contrary to the majority of what is reported in the literature [63, 64]. Nevertheless, the nature of this effect could be associated with the O-rich ambient during the co-precipitation process, in which O acts as vacancies, that are in a higher number, compared with electrons, being the majority charge carriers [65]. Despite this peculiarity, in the trend of S with the NaOH concentration (see Figure 4.a), the Seebeck coefficient experienced a

decrease with the increase in the volume of NaOH added to the solution. For instance, for low addition of NaOH (5 ml) the S is 11 mVK^{-1} . It is observed a decrease of $\sim 63\%$ when the volume of the added NaOH increases when compared with the sample produced with 30 ml. In an opposite direction, in the electrical conductivity trend, an increase is observed with the increase of NaOH concentration, changing from $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mSm}^{-1}$ to $10 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mSm}^{-1}$. It is well-known that for a semiconductor the Seebeck is given by the following equation:

$$|S| = \left(\frac{8\pi^2 \kappa_B^2 T}{3eh^2} \right) m^* (\pi/3n)^{2/3} \quad (8)$$

where κ_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, h is the Planck's constant, e is the unit charge of electron, m^* is the effective mass, and n is the carriers concentration [66].

From equation 8, it is possible to observe that S contribution arises from n or m^* . On the other hand, the conductivity is proportional to the number of carriers ($\sigma = ne\mu_e$; where μ_e is the electron mobility given by $\mu_e = e/m^*\tau$, where τ is the scattering time). One way of disclosing the nature of the effective variations of S and σ is by representing S vs $\sigma^{-2/3}$ (see Figure 4.b), simplifying it to $S = \text{Const. } Tm^{*2/3}\tau^{2/3}(1/\sigma^{2/3})$. Since both quantities were measured at the same temperature and S does not depend directly on τ , the variation arises from the density of charge carriers, as it can be seen by the linear fit in Figure 4.b, meaning that m^* remains constant while n changes with the changes of the microstructures. This behaviour infers that the number of carriers responsible for the transport properties increases when using more concentrated NaOH, during the nanoparticles synthesis, up to 15 ml. This behaviour can arise from the vacancies produced during the synthesis since it is known that the NaOH concentration contributes to a rapid nucleation during the synthesis process. This process could lead to the appearance of a competition between O^-/O^{2-} charge electronegativity and thus the appearance of vacancies and defects, mainly in the O site and on Zn site, that promotes the increase of the number of carriers, as also reported by Koutu *et al.* [67].

Regarding the thermal conductivity, the measurements at room temperature are displayed in Figure 4.c. For 5 ml κ is $\sim 0.7 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, in agreement with values for ZnO microstructures [68], and up until 12ml it is observed a decrease of this property in 28%, reaching $\sim 0.5 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Then, an increase with the increase of the volume of the added NaOH

is observed, reaching for 30 ml a value of $\sim 0.9 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (80% increase). Considering that κ is decomposed in $\kappa_e + \kappa_l$ and the results obtained in the S and σ , it is clear that the variation of κ up until 15 ml could only have phononic nature, since the Wiedemann-Franz law states that $\kappa_e = L\sigma T$ and its behaviour does not correspond to σ . Notice that this is in agreement with the SEM results since the morphology changes directly impact the variations in κ . For volumes above 15 ml, like in the case of electrical conductivity, the increase of the nucleation and cluster size leads to an increase of the κ_l thus approaching the typical values of κ for bulk ZnO reported in the literature ($1-1.2 \times 10^2 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [65]). Density measurements were performed using the samples' mass and volume to evaluate the porosity effect on the thermal conductivity. For the different samples, similar densities were observed, presenting an average density of $\sim 3 \text{ gcm}^{-3}$ (deviations are in the error range). Considering these results are far from the unit cell density ($\sim 5.6 \text{ gcm}^{-3}$), a porosity of around $\sim 54\%$ was obtained. By applying a simple model of the thermal conductivity for composites [69], given by

$$\kappa_{\text{comp}} = (1-f)\kappa_{\text{ZnO}} + f\kappa_{\text{air}} \quad (9)$$

and taking into account the porosity value ($f = 0.54$), $\kappa_{\text{ZnO}} = 1 \times 10^2 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\kappa_{\text{air}} = 0.024 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, the overall calculated κ is $46 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which is much higher than the obtained values ($< 0.9 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). A huge decrease of the phonon contribution for nanoscale sizes ($\sim 10 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for $\sim 50 \text{ nm}$) is theoretically predicted by Wu *et al.*[70]. Moreover, considering the obtained values of porosity, the achieved κ around $0.9 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is in concordance with the works presented by Huang *et al.*[71] e Xu *et al.*[72]. Therefore, one could conclude that, since all the values are below the ones reported in the literature for ZnO and due to the nanoscale dimension of the particles, quantum confinement is observed and responsible for the lower value of κ .

To evaluate the capabilities of ZnO as a TE material, its ZT and PF was calculated, and the results can be observed in Figure 4.d. It is clear the presence of two regions where both quantities seem to behave linearly but with different slopes. In the first region (5 – 12 ml), the ZT presents a higher slope than the PF , meaning that, although the band structure is contributing to an increase of ZT , it is majored by the nanoconfinement effect arising from the morphologic change. However, in the second region (15–30 ml), due to the

establishment of the new structure, PF and ZT follow very similar behaviours, thus showing that it is the band structure that is playing the principal action on the mechanism. It is observed that PF and ZT maximum values of $3.25 \text{ n W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-2}$ and 3.35×10^{-6} , respectively, were achieved.

In order to understand the behaviour of the transport properties of the different samples of the ZnO nanoparticles with the temperature increase, temperature dependence measurements of the Seebeck coefficient and the electrical conductivity were performed. The obtained results are presented in Figure 5.a-b. Firstly, regarding the Seebeck Coefficient, we can see that, for different volumes of NaOH, the behaviours are similar, i.e. a decrease of S with the increase of the temperature, being significant for lower temperature, whereas, for higher temperatures, the values tend slowly to zero. This can be caused by the increase of the electronic charge density which will decrease the energy difference between the Fermi energy and the valence band. Secondly, concerning the electrical conductivity, a general increase with temperature can be seen. This response results from the fact that, when the temperature is increased in a semiconductor, the density of the charge carriers increases and hence the conductivity increases, thus reinforcing the Seebeck decreasing results. Using a thermal activation theory, the activation energy (E_a) for each sample was obtained by plotting $\log\sigma(1000/T)$, as it can be seen in the example for 15 ml in Figure 5.c, where it was obtained a value of approximately 0.45 eV. These results are presented in Figure 6.a, where can be also seen the SEM images of the present structures.

Figure 5: Seebeck Coefficient (a) and Electrical Conductivity (b) as functions of temperature, for different volumes of NaOH. (c) Determination of the Activation Energy (E_a) for the sample with 15 ml of NaOH (linear fit given by the dashed line). The thick lines are a guide to the eye.

The order of magnitude of the presented values is in agreement with the typical value for ZnO, which is around 0.5 eV [73]. A peak at 12 ml (300 meV) can be seen, corresponding to the transition concentration, where a mixture of the hexagonal prismshaped structures and the desert-rose stones occurs. This 80% increase, in relation to the initial value of the 5ml sample, is caused by the presence of a variety of interfaces between the grains, which is more predominant due to the mixture of the different nanostructures, creating a higher energy barrier for the carriers to pass from grain to grain [73], as represented in Figure 6.b.

Figure 6: (a) Activation Energy (E_a) values for the different volumes of NaOH. The values were obtained by plotting $\log\sigma(1000/T)$; (b) Schematic of the phenomenon occurring at the grain boundary of the ZnO nanoparticles. Due to the multiplicity of interfaces between the grains, their boundary becomes more complex, meaning that a higher E_a is needed for the carriers to pass from grain to grain, creating a barrier.

4. Conclusions

In summary, in this work, it was possible to manipulate the preferential direction and the shape of p-type ZnO nanoparticles produced by the co-precipitation method by changing the volume of NaOH added to the process, being possible to achieve a maximum S of $\sim 12 \text{ mVK}^{-1}$. With the increase of NaOH, the nanoparticles change from hexagonal prism-shaped structures, to "desert-rose stones" that tend to cluster. A continuous change of n was revealed from S and σ results. A distinct phenomenon occurred on κ , where a significant reduction in two orders of magnitude compared with the bulk value was achieved, achieving a minimum of $0.5 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Furthermore, when there is a mixture of the two structures, the phononic phenomena predominate, causing a change between the behaviours of PF and ZT , due to the higher contribution of the lattice component of the thermal conductivity. From the temperature dependence outcomes, applying a thermal activation model, it was possible to calculate the activation energy for each sample (values between 120–450 meV), which evidence the complex interfaces between the grains, causing a barrier to the passage of the charge carriers when E_a increases 80% for the sample produced with 15 ml. Finally, Zinc Oxide, herein studied, has very interesting results for high-temperature applications, due to its reproducibility, high stability, high melting point and low-cost production.

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